

THE ISSUE OF RECIDIVISM IN CALIFORNIA

Rebecca Babayan

Crescenta Valley High School, Glendale, California, United States

ABSTRACT

The United States has one of the highest imprisonment rates in the world. Still, a more pressing concern lies in the factors within prisons that perpetuate a cycle of reoffending among formerly incarcerated individuals. To better understand this, the research will examine recidivism, defined as the tendency of released offenders to re-offend. Recidivism is especially high in the first year after release, with 43 percent of former inmates being rearrested within that time (Schanzenbach, 2020). This paper will explore prison conditions, such as access to education and healthcare, that contribute to the challenges of reentry. Additionally, we will discuss external obstacles like housing and employment difficulties, which further drive recidivism. Focusing on California, the most populous state in the U.S., this research will analyze its 41.9% recidivism rate (CDCR) and the specific challenges contributing to this issue.¹

Keywords: *Recidivism, Reintegration, Reentry, Incarcerated, Ex-offenders*

1. INTRODUCTION

Legislation/Normative Framework

Before looking at factors that influence recidivism²It is important to understand the prison structure within the United States. The U.S. criminal justice system works at federal and state levels, with each handling different types of crimes. Federal courts deal with cases involving federal law violations, crimes on federal property, or those that cross state lines. On the other hand, state courts handle crimes within their territories. The Federal Bureau of Prisons (BOP), which manages around 158,000 federal inmates, focuses heavily on addressing behavioral issues during and after incarceration to reduce reoffending, especially since almost half of these inmates are serving time for drug offenses.

¹ This paper was prepared with the guidance of my mentor, Carlos De la Rosa and preparation of Indigo Research. I affirm that all the ideas and writing here is my own.

² Recidivism is one of the most fundamental concepts in criminal justice. It refers to a person's relapse into criminal behavior, often after the person receives sanctions or undergoes intervention for a previous crime (National Institute of Justice).

This dual system of federal and state jurisdictions highlights the complexity of addressing crime and rehabilitation in the U.S. While it allows for organization in terms of crime, it also creates inconsistencies that can lead to unequal sentences and outcomes. For example, drug offenses tend to be punished more harshly at the federal level, which can make effective rehabilitation even more difficult. Additionally, federal prisons tend to have more modern infrastructure compared to their state counterparts. Those who go to federal prisons also tend to be serving longer sentences.

State prisons, like those run by the California Department of Corrections and Rehabilitation (CDCR), have a slightly different focus. They prioritize rehabilitation, education, and reentry programs aimed at creating safer communities through restorative justice. The CDCR emphasizes its goal to build these safer communities by focusing on restorative justice, but there are some clear gaps between the federal and state systems. These differences, including how sentences are handed out and the environments within prisons, often lead to inconsistent results in reintegration.

Adding to the challenge is the fact that federal and state prisons often have very different priorities when it comes to rehabilitation. These differences in how prisons are run can directly impact whether an inmate has a successful reentry into society. Reforms need to be more focused on making real progress in reducing recidivism. Improving prison conditions and creating a more unified approach to sentencing and rehabilitation across both systems would be a big step forward. Otherwise, the system risks keeping people trapped in cycles of inequality and reoffending instead of helping them reintegrate successfully.

2. DISCUSSION

In this section, the paper will explore the structure of education programs in state prisons, along with the health standards in place and how they are maintained. After reviewing general policies, we will focus specifically on California to identify areas where improvements can be made. The goal is to enhance rehabilitation efforts, ensuring that upon release, inmates are better equipped for successful reintegration, ultimately reducing recidivism.

Education

Education serves as the foundational element necessary to curb crime rates. Within this paper, we will be viewing education as high-level courses that will provide inmates with knowledge and facts that can then apply to their lives outside of incarceration. Research indicates

that individuals who do not complete high school are 3.5 times more likely to be arrested than those who graduate (SLJ, 2008). The initial crimes that lead those to prison can be partially attributed to a lack of adequate education. When this lack of education isn't addressed in prison, either because there aren't enough programs or because the programs aren't well-targeted, it's not surprising that many inmates end up back in prison after being released.

Keying in on this root cause of recidivism, the NCES blog highlights a study that reveals that 58% of those in custody no longer receive any form of instruction ("NCES", 2017). This educational deficit has profound implications for the employment prospects of inmates upon their release. Research from Simmons University supports this finding by noting, "Many prisoners have limited education and work experience, which makes it difficult for them to secure employment after they are released. About 70 percent are high school dropouts" (Simmons University, 2016). Education within prison is directly correlated with employment opportunities outside of prison. With a lack of employment and little financial means, many ex-incarcerates choose to commit crimes again.

In California, the Office of Correctional Education explains, "Various academic and education programs exist at each of California's adult state institutions. The goal of OCE is to provide incarcerated individuals with needed education and career training as part of a broader CDCR effort to increase public safety and reduce recidivism"(CDCR). Currently, the CDCR reports that both basic high school level courses along college courses are available for the incarcerated. Through partnerships with local community colleges, inmates can even earn associate degrees that are accredited by the U.S. Department of Education (CDCR). However, while California does provide education, it is evident that recidivism rates are still relatively high. Just in 2018-2019, 16.8% of the formerly incarcerated returned to prison (Petersilia, J.,2008). It is important to recognize that education doesn't only need to exist, but also needs to be organized to be effective outside of prison.

To ensure that educational programs in California's prisons are truly effective, evaluations from both inmates and employers should be done. The California Legislative Analyst's Office highlights the importance of regular, systematic assessments to determine if these rehabilitation programs are helping to reduce recidivism. By establishing a strong framework for evaluations, California can pinpoint which initiatives are working well and which ones need adjustments or should be phased out altogether (Legislative Analyst's Office, 2017).

With more specificity on what types of education are the best for those incarcerated, we can see recidivism decrease immensely. Focusing on not only knowledge-based education but also career-oriented workshops can help those who are released from prison to find employment, which will contribute to lower recidivism rates.

Health

The sudden shift from incarceration to freedom is a difficult challenge on its own. As discussed, education is a necessary factor in ensuring that ex-offenders are capable of finding employment and co-existing with others. However, physical and mental health can also play a large role in whether or not an inmate will reoffend once released. Daniel Wallace, a researcher at the Office of Public Policy explains, “Given the complexity of the reentry process, one's health status, both in and out of prison, likely influences additional aspects of reentry, such as abstaining from crime or adhering to parole terms”(Wallace, D., & Wang, X, 2020). This makes it clear that addressing the health of inmates is a necessary step to break the cycle of recidivism and guide those reentering to a better quality of life.

The Office of Health Care Services for California Correctional institutions states that their mission is “To facilitate the successful reintegration of the individuals in our care back to their communities equipped with the tools to be drug-free, healthy, and employable members of society by providing education, treatment, rehabilitative, and restorative justice programs, all in a safe and humane environment”(CCHS, 2019). While a mention of a safe and humane environment is claimed, it is clear that due to a variety of factors, this mission has not been accomplished. Research indicates that California's rapidly aging prison population is particularly susceptible to chronic illnesses, with about 40 percent of inmates suffering from one or more such conditions—a percentage that aligns with national estimates. (Simon, J, 2016). Furthermore, outside of just chronic illness, problems of physical health are not foreign to inmates with studies from the National Library of Medicine proving that often, lack of proper ventilation and meals that are un-nutritious take away from the physiological well-being of those in prison (Rich, J. D., 2015). With inmates being subject to these conditions in prison, when they are released, their health is still poor leading to added risks of re-offending.

While physiological issues are a major deterrent to success after release from prison, another important factor is mental health and substance dependence issues. A health policy brief delves deep into this issue and reveals that those with mental health problems and substance use

disorders are more commonly seen in justice-involved populations in comparison to the general population (Russ, E. N., et al, 2021). This means that more people who have already been incarcerated are struggling with mental health problems than those who haven't. Additionally, these mental health problems are often intensified due to lack of access to health care after release (Wallace, D., & Wang, X, 2020). While a lack of proper mental well-being is generally linked with the added risk of recidivism, certain disorders are deemed more dangerous. For example, individuals with borderline personality disorder and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder were much more prone to reoffending (Abracen, J, 2014). This goes to show the importance of not only providing more health care for mental issues, such as therapists but also focusing on populations with disorders that have higher risks of recidivism.

Beyond just mental health problems, drug substance issues are common and threatening in incarcerated communities. A study conducted on newly remanded convicts shows that substance abuse is incredibly high (Mason, D., et al., 1997). Unfortunately, inmates enter incarceration with these abuse issues and often carry them due to a lack of help. Statistics from the Bureau of Justice Statistics show that “From 2001 to 2018, the number of people who have died of drug or alcohol intoxication in state prisons rose more than 600%”(Schwartzapfel, B., & Jenkins, J., 2021). This upward rise of drug and alcohol abuse occurring in prisons is incredibly detrimental to the quality of rehabilitation. Due to these issues, California began a Comprehensive Treatment Program across its prison system in January of 2020 according to the CDCR. So far, this program has proven to be successful, with overdose rates dropping 58% (California inmate overdoses., 2022). While there is still a lot to work on before the substance issues in California and other states’ prisons are fixed, this is a promising step forward.

Ensuring convicts are healthy in all regards during their time in prison is necessary for successful reintegration. While the California Prison System has certainly stepped forward with various programs to ensure continual physical and mental health, the efforts aren't perfect. With large prison populations, often the budget becomes the problem leading to issues with enforcement of these programs, availability to all those incarcerated, and resourcefulness. The best way to tackle the problem of programs not living up to the best standard is to have a smaller prison population that can then result in a special focus on each person during rehabilitation. This would in turn mean less incarceration and less recidivism. It is important to realize that

recidivism is mainly resulting from a lack of proper care and getting caught in the cycle can be incredibly harmful.

Outside of Prison: Overview

Recidivism occurs after inmates are released, making it crucial to examine not only the challenges faced during incarceration but also those encountered in everyday life post-release. This section will explore key issues such as employment and housing difficulties, which are significant in the reentry process. By analyzing these factors, we can identify the most effective strategies to help ex-offenders reintegrate into society, reduce recidivism, and build stable, successful lives after prison.

Employment

The reintegration of former convicts into society is a concerning process, particularly due to the significant financial challenges they face. Upon release, many are economically unstable and struggle to regain their footing, largely because finding employment proves difficult. The Brookings Institution highlights that over half of formerly incarcerated individuals fail to secure stable jobs within their first year, primarily due to the societal stigma associated with having a criminal record (Groger, A., et al., 2021). Without employment, these individuals remain financially unstable and find it hard to make meaningful progress, hindering their chances of turning their lives around. William C. Brooks, a professor of social ethics at Harvard, observes that those with a criminal record can lose up to \$100,000 in income during their prime earning years (Brooks, C. W., 2015). This loss severely disadvantages ex-offenders in their efforts to move forward in life. Knowing this, it is incredibly important to look at a possible solution.

One proposed solution to improve reintegration for former offenders is to expand employment opportunities, with the "Ban the Box" policy. This policy, also known as the Fair Chance Act, was implemented in California on January 1st, 2018, before the law became federal on December 17th, 2019 (Fair Chance Act: Criminal history and employment, n.d.). Its removal of the question about criminal history from the initial stages of job applications allows for former inmates to be evaluated based on their skills before their past is considered. This policy is considered to be generally helpful, with the National Conference of State Legislatures reporting a 33% increase in the number of applicants with criminal records who were hired (Ban the Box. , 2021). Furthermore, additional statistics conducted in 2016 at the Harvard Kennedy School showed that "these bans increased employment of residents in high-crime neighborhoods by as

much as 4%”(Shoag, D., & Veuger, S., 2016). This proves that it has helped boost employment for many ex-inmates, within California and beyond, giving them a better chance to successfully reenter society and contribute to the economy. With employment rates up, recidivism will go down, rendering Ban the Box and other solutions to stigma against ex-convicts as incredibly useful tools.

While Ban the Box is helpful to a certain extent, it is imperative to recognize areas in which it could be weaker. Graham Boone, a writer and editor for the U.S. The Bureau of Labor Statistics points out that "ban-the-box" policies lead to a 5.1 percent drop in job opportunities for young Black men without college degrees (Boone, G., 2017). This happens because, without criminal background information, employers may make assumptions, often shaped by racial biases. As a result, minority groups may miss out on the policy's intended economic benefits, making them less likely to support it. At the same time, employers oppose "ban-the-box" policies for different reasons. They want to know if a candidate has a criminal record early in the process, primarily for safety reasons. Steven Raphael, a professor of Public Policy at UC Berkeley, notes that employers "reveal a strong aversion to hiring applicants with criminal records" (Raphael, S., 2011). Without this knowledge upfront, they feel they are wasting time and money reviewing candidates they wouldn't hire anyway. To address this, Lucius Couloute, suggests that governments could offer "incentives for employers who hire people with criminal records" to ease the concerns about financial risks (Couloute, L., & Kopf, D., 2018). These incentives would help ex-offenders find jobs and give employers confidence in their hiring choices. Once this process is implemented in California, we will be able to see the beneficial effects of Ban the Box grow substantially.

Housing

Each year, 600,000 prisoners are released from both state and federal prisons (Office of the Assistant Secretary for Planning and Evaluation. n.d.). In terms of California prisons, that number is 30,000, making up 5% of all the inmates released (Mihalovich, C, 2024). Being able to earn employment and earn money is an important step forward in the process of reintegration for these ex-offenders. However, what happens when they do have money for housing but get denied? A study conducted in California among the homeless community concludes that “And in the six months before becoming homeless, 43% were in jail or prison, or were on probation or parole”(The Biggest Survey, 2023). Those who were formerly incarcerated have higher chances

of falling into the cycle of homelessness. Often no direction is given to them once released, especially because California doesn't require inmates to have housing before release (Weichselbaum, S., Blankstein, A., & Chaidez, A., 2023), ex-inmates find themselves in a rather difficult situation. The main reasons for this have been proven by research to be that public housing authorities and private landlords often discriminate against formerly incarcerated individuals, while the lack of affordable housing exacerbates their exclusion from the rental market (Couloute, L., 2018). With this stigma resulting in discrimination, along with financial issues, it is obvious why so many of the ex-incarcerated are falling into the brutal cycle of homelessness.

The U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development, n.d.) highlights several initiatives to help people find housing when reentering society after prison. One of the most effective approaches is building partnerships between public housing authorities (PHAs) and community organizations. These collaborations help provide formerly incarcerated individuals with the stability and secure housing they need once released, which is essential in preventing them from reoffending. Enterprise, an organization focused on affordable housing, stresses the importance of having a support system. Recently, they launched the H2J National Toolkit, in partnership with the Fortune Society, to help housing providers better understand and serve people impacted by the justice system (Enterprise Community Partners., 2020). Toolkits like these give individuals the resources and guidance to connect with housing options even before they leave prison, making the transition process a lot easier.

In addition to landlord connections, research shows that incentivizing families to take in relatives returning from prison could be a game changer. Not only does family support reduce the cost of housing, but it also offers emotional and social stability, both of which are key for a successful reentry. Studies show that individuals who live with family after being released are less likely to re-offend (Herbert, C. W., et al., 2015). However, the government is not currently incentivizing families of ex-offenders to support them. This highlights just how important a strong, supportive living environment is for released convicts, yet, how they often don't get this wall to lean on.

To better support released offenders in securing housing, California has implemented various post-release programs, including the ³Female Offender Treatment and Employment Program, ⁴Specialized Treatment for Optimized Programming, and the ⁵Long Term Offender Reentry Recovery Program (CDCR). While these initiatives, established over the past two decades, offer vital resources for transitional housing, rehabilitation, and employment assistance, significant challenges remain. Many programs operate with limited capacity, making it difficult for a substantial number of inmates—especially those who do not meet specific demographic criteria—to access them. Additionally, the lack of funding hampers the expansion of these services to all individuals exiting the prison system. This situation is compounded by California's policy of not requiring inmates to have a housing address secured before their release, a contrast to practices in many other states. Implementing such a requirement could lead to a significant decrease in homelessness among the formerly incarcerated, providing them with a stable foundation to rebuild their lives.

3. ANALYSIS

The issue of recidivism in California reflects deep-rooted systemic problems within the correctional system. In our analysis of the differences between state and federal prisons, this becomes clear. With different charges for the same offenses, many inmates are left confused and distrustful of their charges. The atmosphere in prisons often does not contribute positively once admitted. The inconsistent education efforts and unhealthy environments are what we discovered to be the main causes of recidivism once released. Yet again, the discrimination and stigma faced by released offenders from employers and landlords is just another struggle. While California has taken many steps against these negative factors, many imperfections exist.

³ The program offers a smooth transition for women from custody to the community through intensive, gender-responsive counseling, comprehensive case management, and the option for children to reside with their mothers during treatment and recovery for up to 15 months.

⁴STOP(mental and drug use issues) contractors provide comprehensive, evidence-based programming, and services to individuals in their first year of release during their transition into the community to support a successful reentry and reduce recidivism.

⁵ The LATER is a residential program providing housing, meals, supervision, and support services in a safe, drug-free environment, offering long-term parolees assistance with employment, stress management, victim awareness, life skills, substance abuse education, and a certified 52-week domestic violence program based on assessed needs.

By looking at countries where recidivism is low, we may get a better understanding of how to further better our system. One such country where we see low recidivism rates is Norway (World Population Review., 2023). In a study conducted, Norway's recidivism in the first two years was 17.6% in comparison to 52.9% in the United States (Yakhnenko, D., Leen Farouki, & Fazel, S., 2023) and 41.9% in California (CDCR). We can attribute these low rates to Norway's focus on rehabilitation. The design of the prison system is explained to be a focus on Restorative justice. This means that Norway treats prisons as rehabilitation centers, prioritizing reintegration over punishment. It aims to help former convicts become stable members of society by designing cells that resemble dorm rooms, often without bars. For example, Halden, a maximum-security prison, provides inmates with private toilets, showers, fridges, and flat-screen TVs, along with shared kitchens and common spaces (Dorjsuren, B., 2020). By implementing a similar model into the American Prison system, particularly in California, we can expect a major reduction in recidivism, keeping our prisons clear and eventually even coming to benefit our economy.

Realistically, Norway and the United States differ in many ways, so the same system being implemented would be difficult. With Norway being a smaller country and having lower crime rates, it is easier to make such well-structured and community-oriented prisons. Furthermore, due to fewer criminals needing cells, economically it is also not as challenging. Within the United States, many cells and prisons are needed for the ever-growing population of prisoners, making this a significantly more expensive matter. While we may not be able to create the same system, we can take the root ideas of what we see in Norway and apply them here. Putting an emphasis not on punishment but on rehabilitation and creating a community is the largest factor in this. Through this means, we may be able to see recidivism go down, and with fewer inmates, we can direct money to bigger, nicer cells. Cutting out the root of the problem rather than waiting until these prisoners are set out into society and unable to support themselves is what our focus should be.

4. CONCLUSION

Many people overlook prisoner reintegration as a serious issue, but it has significant implications for our society. It reflects issues within our justice system and has

negative economic impacts. While we have worked towards solving this issue in the past few decades, the initiative has often fallen short.

This research indicates that the education and health standards within prisons are still lacking and not reaching every inmate. Additionally, we must address the stigma that prevents ex-offenders from securing employment and housing after their release. We need to work from both the inside and the outside to ensure that the system we have in place is not based on punishment, but rather, on rehabilitation that leaves individuals well-equipped for reintegration into society. It's time to truly invest in their success.

5. LIMITATIONS

This analysis while credible has certain limitations that need to be addressed. Since the data primarily comes from California, its relevance to other states with different policies and infrastructures might be limited. Additionally, a lot of the information relies on past studies and statistics and while we did look at some recent policy changes, not all could be covered. This may render it unable to capture the full scope of prison conditions and post-release support. The final limitation is the focus on institutional factors, meaning there may be an overlook in important personal aspects, such as support networks or mental resilience. Ultimately, while these limitations exist, this comprehensive review of recidivism in California can still be applied to other states and the measurable patterns are essential for assessing reintegration outcomes and how to better them.

References

- Abracen, J., Langton, C. M., Looman, J., Gallo, A., Ferguson, M., Axford, M., & Dickey, R. (2014). Mental health diagnoses and recidivism in paroled offenders. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 58(7), 765–779. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X13485930>
- Ban the box. (2021). National Conference of State Legislatures. <https://www.ncsl.org/civil-and-criminal-justice/ban-the-box>
- Boone, G. (2017). How banning boxes encourages discrimination. *Monthly Labor Review*. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/90001350>
- Brooks, C. W. (2015). Ban the box. In I. Chettiar et al. (Eds.), *Solutions: American leaders speak out on criminal justice* (pp. 13–18). Brennan Center for Justice. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep28423.7>
- California Department of Corrections and Rehabilitation - California Department of Corrections and Rehabilitation. (2019). California Department of Corrections and Rehabilitation. <https://www.cdcr.ca.gov>
- California inmate overdoses plummet under drug program. (2022). AP News. <https://apnews.com/article/covid-health-prisons-california-gavin-newsom-cd5488a58681a16394c0acb5ce62a5dc>
- CCHCS | California Correctional Health Care Services. (2019). Ca.gov. <https://cchcs.ca.gov/>
- Couloute, L. (2018). Nowhere to Go: Homelessness among formerly incarcerated people. Prison Policy Initiative. <https://www.prisonpolicy.org/reports/housing.html>
- Couloute, L., & Kopf, D. (2018). Out of prison & out of work: Unemployment among formerly incarcerated people. Prison Policy Initiative. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep27307>
- Dorjsuren, B. (2020). Norway's prison system benefits its economy. The Borgen Project. <https://borgenproject.org/norways-prison-system/>

- Enterprise Community Partners. (2020). Enterprise Community Partners. <https://www.enterprisecommunity.org/about/what-we-do>
- Fair Chance Act: Criminal history and employment. (n.d.). https://calcivilrights.ca.gov/wp-content/uploads/sites/32/2022/11/Fair-Chance-Act-FAQ_ENG.pdf
- Groger, A., et al. (2021). A better path forward for criminal justice: Prisoner reentry. Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/a-better-path-forward-for-criminal-justice-prisoner-re-entry/>
- Herbert, C. W., et al. (2015). Homelessness and housing insecurity among former prisoners. RSF: The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences, 1(2), 44–79. <https://doi.org/10.7758/rsf.2015.1.2.04>
- Legislative Analyst's Office. (2017). Improving in-prison rehabilitation programs. LAO Publications. <https://lao.ca.gov/Publications/Report/3720>
- Mason, D., et al. (1997). Substance use in remand prisoners: A consecutive case study. BMJ: British Medical Journal, 315(7099), 18–21. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25175062>
- Mihalovich/CalMatters, C. (2024). Are California prisons stiffing inmates on \$200 release payments? Lawsuit says they are. AP News. <https://apnews.com/us-news/lawsuits-california-legal-proceedings-general-news-0a660bafa2451a896fe69e50699b902d>
- National Institute of Justice. (n.d.). Recidivism. National Institute of Justice. <https://nij.ojp.gov/topics/corrections/recidivism>
- Office of the Assistant Secretary for Planning and Evaluation. (n.d.). Incarceration & reentry. ASPE. <https://aspe.hhs.gov/topics/human-services/incarceration-reentry-0>
- Petersilia, J. (2008). California's correctional paradox of excess and deprivation. Crime and Justice, 37(1), 207–278. <https://doi.org/10.1086/520944>

- Raphael, S. (2011). Incarceration and prisoner reentry in the United States. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 635, 192–215. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/29779418>
- Rich, J. D., Allen, S. A., & Williams, B. A. (2015). The Need for Higher Standards in Correctional Healthcare to Improve Public Health. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 30(4), 503–507. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-014-3142-0>
- Russ, E. N., et al. (2021). Prison and jail reentry and health. *Health Affairs*. <https://www.healthaffairs.org/content/briefs/prison-and-jail-reentry-and-health>
- Schanzenbach, D., et al. (2023). Twelve facts about incarceration and prisoner reentry. Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/twelve-facts-about-incarceration-and-prisoner-reentry>
- Schwartzapfel, B., & Jenkins, J. (2021). Overdose deaths in state prisons have jumped dramatically since 2001. NPR. <https://www.npr.org/2021/07/15/1015447281/overdose-deaths-state-prisons-increase>
- Simon, J. (2016). California's new carceral logic: Health care, confinement, and the future of imprisonment. *Boom: A Journal of California*, 6(2), 22–31. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26413169>
- Simmons University. (2016). The Challenges of Prisoner Reentry Into Society. Online.simmons.edu; Simmons University. <https://online.simmons.edu/blog/Prisoner-Reentry/>
- Shoag, D., & Veuger, S. (2016). No woman no crime: Ban the box, employment, and upskilling. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2782599>
- SLJ. (2008). Crime Linked to Dropout Rates, Report Says. *School Library Journal*. <https://www.slj.com/story/crime-linked-to-dropout-rates-report-says>
- The biggest survey of homeless Californians in decades shows why so many are on the streets. (2023). KPBS Public Media.

<https://www.kpbs.org/news/local/2023/06/20/the-biggest-survey-of-homeless-californians-in-decades-shows-why-so-many-are-on-the-streets>

U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development. (n.d.). Reentry housing. U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development. <https://www.hud.gov/reentry>

Wallace, D., & Wang, X. (2020). Does in-prison physical and mental health impact recidivism? *SSM - Population Health*, 11(100569), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2020.100569>

Weichselbaum, S., Blankstein, A., & Chaidez, A. (2023). California's prison-to-homelessness pipeline. *NBC News*. <https://www.nbcnews.com/news/investigations/californias-prison-homelessness-pipeline-rcna93975>

World Population Review. (2023). Recidivism rates by country 2023. [Worldpopulationreview.com](https://worldpopulationreview.com). <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/recidivism-rates-by-country>

Yakhnenko, D., Leen Farouki, & Fazel, S. (2023). Criminal recidivism rates globally: A 6-year systematic review update. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 88(1), 102115–102115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2023.102115>